

The Degree Of Applicability Of The Values Of Vocational Education In The Light Of Islamic Education In Secondary Schools In The Northern Region From The Point Of View Of Vocational Education Supervisors And Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Degree Of Application, Vocational Education, Islamic Education, Secondary Vocational Schools.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5209508</p>	<p><i>The study aimed at the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education, and the study adopted the descriptive survey method, and the researchers prepared a questionnaire for the values of vocational education, where the study community consisted of all supervisors and teachers of vocational education. In secondary schools in the North Region, which numbered (12) male and female supervisors, and (820) male and female teachers, and the study sample consisted of (383) supervisors and teachers. The results of the study showed that the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools came with a score of High; The results revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education due to the gender variable, and came in favor of males, and there were no differences due to the variables of experience and job title. The researchers recommend the need for the Ministry of Education to work on developing positive attitudes towards vocational education, and to clarify its importance in the Holy Qur'an and the honorable Sunnah of the Prophet.</i></p>

Introduction

Islam is a comprehensive and integrated religion that includes all aspects of human life. Islam always wants to build a noble, sound and noble society, it instills in its members a distinguished moral and a good example from an early age. Vocational education is a type of education that works on learning different professions, Islam gave professions and professions attention, respect and appreciation, and valued work and its companions, and urged them to adhere to the values of education, as it is a cornerstone for the stability and progress of nations. Therefore, a person must choose his profession and work according to his inclinations, desires, tendencies, and abilities; Because it is one of the things necessary for the success and creativity of the worker, and vocational education was considered the most important element in providing individuals with the experiences and capabilities necessary to succeed in his work.

And the development that societies have witnessed in recent years in the cognitive and technological systems, as indicated by Al-Kharouf and Al-Dahamish (2013), the significant impact on changing the lifestyle of the individual and society, the future worker had to possess all the skills and behaviors that are commensurate with the latest technology used. It was necessary to prepare the citizen well, capable of using modern technology; since the workforce is able to deal with this technology to keep pace with development, it was necessary to find an appropriate solution to the economic and social problems facing the individual and society, through the preparation of qualified and trained manpower, here, the importance of vocational education emerged as an essential part of solving all problems, which played a major role in preparing the human force, as the human being is the focus of the development process.

The efforts of the countries of the world in general and the Arab countries in particular were notable in the development of education, both in terms of full absorption of preparation as well as improving the quality of education. The development of vocational education was linked to graduating individuals with technical and behavioral skills and securing them with specific qualifications to meet the needs of the local market. however, vocational education did not receive sufficient attention, as it was associated with the idea of academic failure, and that it did not give the desired social, cultural and material level of individuals, and vocational education did not receive much attention in government institutions until it was too late (Halabi, 2012).

Therefore, vocational education has become one of the necessities of life in the modern era, considering the human element as the real basis for development, and that it is the real revolution for the homeland, and it is both an end and a means for development, so vocational education occupied an important place in the

educational policies of all countries to provide many solutions to the educational system and fields of work, and that it is a necessity for society to provide the workforce that works to implement human and community development plans, the importance of vocational education in all aspects stems from the fact that it provides it with qualified human energy to be the individual capital and the effective element in the progress of society, which can only be achieved if technical expertise is provided to all fields. one of the main requirements for vocational education programs is to design programs, prepare them in advance, identify resources for these programs, and provide qualified teachers (Mraian, 2010).

Islam linked the real value of a person to his ability to work, and not to what he owns of interests, money or clan, so work was related to the capabilities and energy of the individual only, to God Almighty says: (But those who believed and did righteous deeds - We charge no soul except [within] its capacity. Those are the companions of Paradise; they will abide therein eternally)(Al-A'rāf :42), Islam did not differentiate between males and females in work, as everyone is required to work, to God Almighty says: (And whoever does righteous deeds, whether male or female, while being a believer - those will enter Paradise and will not be wronged, [even as much as] the speck on a date seed) (An-Nisā: 124), Therefore, Islam has been on perfection and diligence in work, regardless of its quality and level. Allah says: (Indeed, those who have believed and done righteous deeds - indeed, We will not allow to be lost the reward of any who did well in deeds) (Al-Kahf,30).

The wisdom in Islam regarding the legalization of work is to communicate what is in it of profit and safety from unemployment that leads to curiosity and self-destruction, and abstaining from that question, and that is why work in Islam is considered one of the elements of Islamic life. Islam sanctifies work at all levels, starting with manual work until the end of all works, there was no separation between intellectual work and manual work. Manual work is respected and appreciated by people, contrary to what was described by various educational philosophies, work, both manual and intellectual, has been considered a basis in the ideas and philosophy of nations, and that the law of work is linked to its output as long as it is within the framework of halal and does not prejudice the social and religious values of the community. The success of Islamic societies in the early centuries in building prosperous Islamic societies included many professions, this was the reason why Muslims agreed with the Qur'anic verses and hadiths that call for work and professions. Islam does not conflict with halal earning and is in line with all societal systems, as it made it a devotional ritual, which prompted Muslims to engage in various professions (Al-Saadi, 2014).

Al-Tweissi (2011) pointed out that the divine approach clarified the importance of professions and professions, and the necessity of learning and teaching them, and considered work a necessity for honorable earning, and placing it in his home is one of the houses of worship, there are many wise Quranic verses and hadiths that stress the importance of work, professions and professions, islamic education bears principles and trends that are completely consistent with what is called today in modern education, only modern education links between science and work and between theory and application as well as Islam, which did not separate between science and work or between theory and application and because it considers science is the only way to advance the individual and society alike.

And Jordan realized the importance of vocational education since its establishment, and gave it great care, and that was clear after 1952 where the Jordanian Ministry of Education worked to increase the number of students enrolled in vocational education to meet the needs of the labor market and increase economic development. In 1987, the Educational Development Conference was prepared, one of his most important decisions was the need to expand vocational education with a focus on developing awareness of the importance of vocational education among students. The Ministry approved extending the stage of basic education to become ten years after that, the student goes to vocational education according to his desires, abilities, inclinations, and the specialization he desires in accordance with the foundations and laws set by the ministry (Vocational Education Department, 2012). Vocational education is defined as a process of preparing an individual for a specific profession or craft by providing him with a set of experiences in an official institutional manner supervised by the Ministry of Education, and the duration of his study lasts for two years (Kennedy, 2011). It is also known as: Part of the general formal education that aims to prepare the individual for employment in a job that fits with the vocational preparation programs in line with the needs and requirements of society (Lohithakshan, 2002). It is also known as one of the secondary education tracks and the duration of its study is two years. Those who successfully complete their requirements are entitled to continue their education at higher levels in universities and colleges (GTZ, 2009).

When we look at vocational education in Jordan, we find that the enrollment of students in this education compared to academic education, which grants an academic degree and an excellent social position in society, is lower. The continuation of this view to the present time has reduced the level of income for the individual and society, so the Ministry of Education established vocational schools To prepare a strategy for developing this education, which in turn works to select the appropriate vocational education for future students (Al-Kharouf and Al-Dahamsheh, 2013).

Therefore, the Jordanian Ministry of Education sought to expand the opening of vocational secondary schools throughout the Kingdom, and strived to attract students of all levels of education, for a course in supplying the

labor market with trained professional cadres capable of supplementing society with trained and qualified manpower, therefore, it became the main part in achieving comprehensive development. The interest in vocational education decreased since the end of the nineteenth century, and increased interest in it in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, so the comprehensive concept of vocational education was defined, its objectives were defined by linking them to the needs of the local market for comprehensive development. Since the establishment of the Jordanian state at the beginning of the twentieth century, it has been concerned with vocational education in order to keep pace with the development and acceleration witnessed by the labor market and the world of professions, where the first school specialized in vocational education was established in (1924) and was called the School of Makers and Arts, and the interest in this education was assigned to several parties, namely: the Ministry of Education, which is concerned with providing vocational education in both practical and theoretical terms, and the Vocational Training Corporation, which is concerned with providing professional programs in order to provide manpower and trained and the Ministry of Higher Education, which is concerned with providing technical graduates (Tweissi, 2013).

Vocational education teachers and supervisors must be keen on applying Islamic values derived from the Holy Qur'an and the honorable Sunnah of the Prophet, due to their great impact in urging students to go to vocational education because it is the profession of the prophets and messengers, it removes the societal view of it. The researcher believes that there is a set of values applied in vocational secondary schools that vary among themselves, which led to the failure to properly place vocational education in the educational system; this is due to the students' lack of knowledge of the importance of vocational education, and the inability to organize it by the authorities in charge of it in terms of following up on its outputs and knowing their suitability to the Jordanian labor market. Therefore, work must be done to increase the number of students enrolled in it, and raising the percentage of its graduates who are enrolled in the labor market, which in turn helps to develop the local economy in all its branches: agricultural, commercial, economic, tourism and health, especially since most secondary school students in Jordan are currently heading to academic branches, the same is true with regard to post-secondary education. On the other hand, vocational education has remained declining and the percentage of students enrolled in it is low. The view was formed inferior to vocational education, and to employers in this field, resulting from several things, the most important of them was the lack of clarity in the concept of vocational education, the principles and foundations on which it is based. The existing system in the Jordanian Ministry of Education is based on sending students with low achievement to vocational education, and other matters, which led to the creation of an inferior view within the Jordanian Ministry of Education and the Jordanian society, and this contradicts the status of vocational education in Islamic education.

1. Study problem and questions

Therefore, this study came to identify the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers. By answering the following questions:

First question: What is the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers?

Second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers due to the variables (gender, job title, experience)?

3. The Objectives of the study:

-Identifying the degree to which the values of vocational education can be applied in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers, in order to enhance them to be of a positive nature to them.

- To reveal the significance of the differences between the sexes, job title and experience, the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region, in order to investigate and identify these differences.

4. The importance of studying:

First: the theoretical significance: The importance of the study comes to contribute to enriching the field of specialization and theoretical literature with studies on the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education, as there are values that are applied to students by teachers of vocational education, and in fact, they are not clear and have no connection with Islamic education, they are values that follow philosophical schools that were imported and dressed in an Islamic character to apply them in schools and oblige those in charge of them, this study, according to the limits of the researcher's knowledge, is one of the recent studies conducted on the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers.

Second: Practical importance: It is hoped that this study will benefit from this study, the planners of vocational education and vocational education curricula, the authorities concerned with modifying and developing curricula in accordance with Islamic values, and the committees concerned with vocational education and its development. It is also hoped that graduate students who enroll in vocational education at universities will benefit from this study, by conducting more research and scientific studies in this field. Research centers and government and private institutions concerned with vocational education may also benefit from this study. It is also hoped that graduates of vocational education and workers in the industrial and professional sectors will benefit from it, by presenting their experiences to specialists and experts and drawing plans that lead to the development of their sectors through vocational education in accordance with Islamic values.

5. The limits of the study:

- **Objective limits:** The degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education.

- **Human limits:** a sample of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in the northern region.

- **Spatial limits:** This study was applied in secondary vocational schools in the Northern Territory.

- **Time limits:** This study was implemented in the second semester of 2020/2021.

6. Idiomatic and Procedural Definitions

-**The degree of application:** It is the total score obtained by supervisors and teachers of vocational secondary schools by responding to the paragraphs of the study tool related to the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region.

- **Vocational education idiomatically:** It is that formal education that aims to prepare and train students to be ready workers and ready to compete in the labor market (Hamid, Aribowo, & Desmira, 2017). procedurally: It is a type of formal education that provides theoretical information and practical training directed at the Jordanian labor market, it includes study programs in various agricultural, industrial, commercial and hotel sectors in line with scientific and technological progress, under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, and students enroll in it after completing the basic school stage.

- **Values of vocational education in the light of procedural Islamic education:** they are the values derived from the Noble Qur'an and the Noble Prophetic Sunnah.

- **Vocational secondary schools:** All schools affiliated to the Ministry of Education, which provide theoretical and practical information regarding vocational education, and students enroll in them after completing the basic school stage.

-**Vocational education supervisors:** an educational supervisor who is scientifically qualified in the professional field, to follow up on his subordinates, including teachers, administrators, and workers, and to direct their achievement and functional development, to raise their effectiveness in achieving the desired educational goals.

-**Vocational education teachers:** They are the teachers who are entrusted with the task of teaching students in vocational secondary schools and preparing them appropriately to keep pace with scientific and technological development.

7. Theoretical framework and previous studies:

7.1: Professional education and understandable

Vocational education is of great importance in the field of comprehensive national development because it provides a workforce with the ability to work in various areas of life, which are agriculture, health, industry and others, because of the importance of this education in various fields, it was necessary to reform it quickly in order to supplement society with manpower that possesses the experience and capabilities necessary to keep pace with the requirements of the labor market, it is necessary to work on reconsidering the education system, its foundations, its methods, and its outputs because of their benefit to the members of society and the state, the education system in general is considered part of the formation of any society with a cultural or intellectual system reinforced by historical experiences that witnessed the disparity between success and failure, and it is a coherent and integrated process that enters into a high level of knowledge matters and a social necessity in all countries alike, vocational education is essential today; Because one of its objectives is to adequately absorb technology, deal with it and develop it, and work to meet the requirements of work and acquire general and specialized skills to meet the needs of the labor market.

The world has recently witnessed an increasing interest in technical and vocational education, especially in the last decades, as part of the attempts made by all industrialized countries to keep pace with rapid technological development and progress in order to exploit the available natural resources and harness them in civilized construction, to achieve a better life for the citizen, the interest in vocational education at its various levels and patterns was reflected in the transformations experienced by the international community, he proceeded from the conviction that preparing manpower trained to deal with technology is the key to renaissance in all sectors (The Arab Conference for Youth Employment, 2009).

Hence, countries' recognition of the importance of vocational education and practical training in achieving the social and economic development of individuals and their communities, as it has become an essential part in the lifelong education process, the Montego Bay Declaration, which contains a set of recommendations to help harness the power and potential of technical and vocational education and training in order to build and maintain a sustainable future for all, was approved (University of the West Indies UNESCO, 2012, para. 8).

7.2: Vocational education concepts:

Al-Smadi (2012) indicated that vocational education is a process by which individuals are qualified to practice a profession, by providing them with practical skills that help them keep pace with the labor market and keep pace with scientific development.

It is also known as a type of formal education under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, and vocational education and training institutions at the secondary level, with the aim of preparing trained professionals, and providing them with skills in various industrial, agricultural, administrative, hotel and home disciplines, and they have the ability to work and produce; To supply them to the Jordanian labor market (Mahasna, 2010).

As for (Kotsikis, 2007), he defined it as including all forms of education that aims to provide students with the qualifications and abilities required for a particular profession that enables them to practice it without regard to their age and level of training.

It is defined as the education that exists in order to prepare employees at the minimum levels required for one or more professions (David Seyi, 2014).

It is also known as one of the two-year secondary education paths, upon completion of its requirements to enter universities and colleges (GTZ, 2009).

Al-Ardi (2004) pointed out that vocational education is the educational system that gives students manual and mental skills and professional ability in order to prepare skilled workers in various disciplines, which makes them able to carry out all the tasks required of them.

7.3 Vocational education in Islam:

The developed and developing countries have worked to pay attention to vocational education, as it works to prepare the human forces that, in turn, work to meet the needs of society and thus work on the construction of the earth Allah says (when your Lord said to the angels, "Indeed, I will make upon the earth a successive authority They said, "Will You place upon it one who causes corruption therein and sheds blood, while we exalt You with praise and declare Your perfection He said, "Indeed, I know that which you do not know)(Al-Baqarah,30)Vocational education from the Islamic point of view had a great role in the progress of nations because of its contribution to improving all areas of social life, as did previous nations when they followed divine laws and regulations and became at the forefront of nations and no one could compete with them because the Islamic religion worked to raise the value of profession, business and professionals because it is considered pillar of society,When we observe the civilized history of previous nations, we notice that the Islamic countries led the world towards safety and tranquility, as they followed the Islamic system, and when they abandoned it, they became among the developing countries.

Islamic education has carried principles and trends towards vocational education that are compatible with what is called modern education in our era. It has linked science and work in theory and practice, since Islam has no separation between one of its molecules, and this is what modern education emphasized to bridge the gap between theoretical and practical learning. Respect for manual work and the reliance of individuals on themselves to be useful to themselves, their families and society, the formation of the individual for life, production and work is achieved only when science is linked to work and production, because he needs to live and think about the hereafter (Al-Ahwani, 1983).

Islam has lofty principles in the values of work and affirmed that a person has nothing but striving and that all the good that a person obtains is associated with what he does of good work for God Almighty and beneficial to him and society Allah says:(And that there is not for man except that for which he strives)(An-Najm,39) Work is the strongest level of worship in Islam, so God Almighty commanded us His servants to strive and actually practice work after prayerAllah says:(And when the prayer has been concluded, disperse within the land and seek from the bounty of Allāh, and remember Allāh often that you may succeed) (Al-Jumu'ah,10)

7.4Vocational education in Jordan

Vocational education has become one of the necessities of life in the modern era based on the consideration that the human element is the real basis for development and that it is the real revolution of the country and it is both an end and a means for development. Therefore, vocational education occupied an important place in the educational policies of all countries to provide many solutions to the educational system and fields of work And it is a necessity for society to provide the workforce that works to implement human and community development plans.

Vocational education is the main component and component of providing students with skills and knowledge in all sectors, as it is the only source that works to provide technical and trained manpower on sound foundations, the Jordanian Ministry of Education sought to provide vocational education to be available to all individuals in order to reduce unemployment and develop the workforce, as it is part of contributing to the economic and

social development of the community, and work on the need to develop vocational education programs in line with the latest developments in the world towards vocational education by supplementing students who possess the knowledge and skills they need in all sectors, as it is the main source of providing the labor market with trained manpower (Khaza'ala and Damour, 2019).

Where vocational education in Jordan sought to provide students with practical skills and basic values, to adapt to society in light of rapid changes, it enables them to develop themselves, appreciate professions and their ethics, provide them with the knowledge that helps them choose the path of their education according to their trends, desires and tendencies, help them think critically, and understand their surroundings with modern technologies, therefore, vocational education was introduced within the secondary education stage in vocational schools within the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, to be the link between theory and practice in various other professions, expanding the horizons for the individual and linking individuals in the community by helping them clarify the reality of the surrounding environment, especially that the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan is one of the developed countries that worked on developing vocational education for its role in raising students' awareness of the new and different professions that are going on around them (Ministry of Education, 2010).

7.5 Objectives of vocational education

Vocational education has goals at the local and global levels, and vocational education seeks to achieve them by preparing qualified manpower within the levels required for the profession and craft, and preparing students for applied and university studies according to their desire and abilities in order to achieve these goals (Al-Masry, 2005, 39).

- Acquiring the correct habits such as accuracy and safety at work and applying the foundations of the economy.
- Buttocks learners with sufficient skills and information about the labor market and professions in it.
- Providing students with practical skills to help them use tools and devices.
- Develop positive attitudes among working individuals to respect work and consider it one of the main basic values from which society derives directions for its growth and development.
- Contribute to achieving a balanced development of individual capabilities, moral values and ease of obtaining skills that suit his needs and desires.
- Harmonizing the skills that the student possesses with the needs of society and the requirements of social and economic development.

8. Previous studies:

Al-Shurman study (2020) to identify the reality of vocational education in Jordan, problems and solutions from the point of view of experts and its supervisors. The study sample consisted of (52) individuals from vocational education experts and their supervisors. The results of the study showed that the reality of vocational education in Jordan on the tool as a whole came with a degree Medium and in all fields, as the field of the influence of expatriate workers on the needs of the labor market came in the first place and at a high degree, while the field of the prevailing view of vocational education in Jordan came in the fourth place with a medium degree of appreciation, and the results of the study revealed the existence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), in the reality of vocational education in Jordan, attributed to the variable of sex, and it came in favor of females, and the results showed that there were statistically significant differences due to the variable of job location and came in favor of the employees of the National Company, and the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the reality of vocational education due to the variable of experience. Study Rintala&Nokelainen (2020) conducted a study aimed at knowing the status of vocational education and training in Finland. The study relied on the descriptive approach, and data was collected through interviews. The study sample consisted of (96) individuals from providers of vocational education and training, and teachers. The results showed that the design of the learning and vocational training environment in Finland focuses on the compatibility between school and work. However, there are attitudes and practices that impede the interrelationship between education and work, and leave the responsibility of reconciling different professional experiences to Learner. Study Al-Qurani and others (2017) conducted a study aimed at determining the role of technology school principals in promoting vocational education from the teachers' point of view within the Green Line. The researchers used the descriptive survey method, and the study sample consisted of (327) teachers distributed over (20) technology schools. The researchers developed a questionnaire as a tool for the study consisting of (40) paragraphs, and the results of the study reached to the attitudes of teachers in the technological schools within the green line on the areas of learning styles were medium, and that there were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in all areas of the role of principals Technological schools in promoting vocational education according to the variable of gender and academic qualification from the point of view of teachers, and there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in any of the fields. The role of school principals from the teachers' point of view is due to the experience variable. Study Al-Sharman and Al-Hussainat (2016) conducted a study that sought to identify the reasons for students' reluctance to enroll in vocational and technical education in Jordanian society from the perspective of Al-Balqa Applied University students, and their relationship to some variables such as gender, place of residence, income and specialization,

where a questionnaire consisting of (19) items was used, and was chosen The sample, in a simple random way, consisted of (200) male and female students. The results revealed a high level of reasons for the reluctance of university students to enroll in vocational and technical education. Study Gavin and Moodie (2016) aimed to understand the status of vocational education in many countries and the different ways in which the relationship between vocational education and the labor market mediates in the changing results achieved by graduates of vocational education. The researchers used the descriptive analytical approach, and the study sample consisted (520).) an individual, and used the questionnaire to understand the status of vocational education, and the results of the study indicated inequality in access to vocational education in countries with high, middle and low-income degrees, and confirmed that government vocational education institutions are the most powerful major institutions in society that can support vocational education teachers to contribute to development Social, economic and cultural, and the results of the study found inequality in access to vocational education in countries with high, middle and low-income degrees, and confirmed that government vocational education institutions are the most powerful main institutions in society that can support vocational education teachers and contribute to local social, economic and cultural development, Propose an international education program in order to better understand vocational education in different contexts, and support Education in working with the company to promote a cycle in the development of inclusive and tolerant societies based on socially equitable and socially sustainable economic and social development. Study Al-Budairi (2015) aimed to know the origins of vocational education in Islam, and the researcher used the historical and descriptive-analytical method, and the results of the study reached to determine the place of professional education in educational philosophies and the role of professional education in Russia, Arab and American educational systems, and clarifying the religious origins of professional education in Islam. Study Al-Sharif (2013) aimed to identify the right to work and the status of crafts and professions in Islam - a jurisprudential study -, and the researcher used the historical method. Accordingly, work is a right for every Muslim, and the restrictions and controls of the right to work in Islam have been updated, and that work is linked to social justice and that it is the source of social wealth. Study Ben Yahya (2013) a study aimed at knowing the theory of work in Islam and its role in the development of society, and the researcher used the analytical method, and the results of the study concluded that work in Islam is no less important than worship, a statement of work theory and its role and positive reflection on the Muslim community, and the role of conquest Islam in the development of the West towards work as a necessary means to achieve self-sufficiency, and that work is a means to achieve closeness to God Almighty. Study Abu Shaira (2010) a study aimed at shedding light on vocational education in Islamic educational thought and contemporary Western educational thought. The researcher used the historical method with the help of description and analysis. The results of the study concluded that all types of work are comprehensive in the Islamic and contemporary view of vocational education, that many Countries with contemporary Western educational thought have roots affected by Islamic educational thought, and the reason is due to their agreement with many educational principles, such as combining theory, practice, and professional guidance.

What distinguishes the study from previous studies: Previous studies talked about vocational education and its reality and importance, such as the study (Al-Shurman 2020, Rintala&Nokelainen 2020, Gavin and Moodie 2016, Reko 2016), and studies about work in Islam and its status and importance to nations, such as the study (Al-Badiri 2015, Al-Sharif 2013, Ben Yahya 2013, Abu Shaira 2010). The current study agreed with most studies on vocational education, such as (Al-Shurman and Al-Hussainat 2016, Al-Shurman 2020) and vocational education in Islam, such as the study (Abu Shaira 2010, Bin Yahya 2013). This study was distinguished from previous studies by referring to the Holy Qur'an and the Prophet's Sunnah to determine the values of vocational education in Islam.

9. Method and procedures

9.1 Study Methodology: In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used the descriptive survey method, which is the most suitable for this study.

9.2 Study community: The study population consisted of all supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools in the North Region, where the number of supervisors was (12) supervisors, and the number of teachers was (820) teachers, (according to the statistics of the Jordanian Ministry of Education for the year 2021 AD).

9.3 The study sample: The study sample was selected from (383) supervisors and teachers, and it was chosen by the available random method, and table (1), and playing rings distributed according to the study variables:

Table (1): Distribution of the study sample by gender, experience, and job title

Variable	Level/Category	Number
Sex	Male	250
	Female	133
Experience	Less than 5 years	132

	5 to 10 years	136
	More than 10 years	115
Job title	Teacher	371
	Supervisor	12

8.4 Study tool: The researchers referred to the alquranalkarim and the Sunnah alnabawia of the Prophet to determine the values of vocational education and formulate the paragraphs of the questionnaire, and the tool consisted in its initial form of (48) paragraphs.

8.5 The validity of the study tool: To validate the content validity of the Professional Education Values Tool; It was presented to a group of (11) arbitrators in the fields of (management and pedagogy, measurement and evaluation, and teaching methods) in a number of Jordanian universities, they were asked to give their opinions about the tool in terms of language and clarity, and any modifications they saw fit. The researcher adopted the paragraph that was agreed upon by (8) arbitrators or more, i.e. (80%) of the arbitrators. Thus, the tool became composed of (45) paragraphs.

8.6 The construction validity of the study tool: The study tool was applied to a pilot sample consisting of (50) male and female teachers, and (4) supervisors from outside the target study sample, in order to calculate the corrected correlation coefficients for the relationship of items with the professional education values tool, as shown in Table (2).

Table (2): The values of the corrected correlation coefficients for the relationship of the items with the Vocational Education Values Tool

Paragraph No.	Corrected link coefficient value	Paragraph No.	Corrected link coefficient value	Paragraph No.	Corrected link coefficient value
1	0.56	16	0.61	31	0.64
2	0.57	17	0.68	32	0.58
3	0.57	18	0.70	33	0.54
4	0.57	19	0.62	34	0.59
5	0.58	20	0.61	35	0.63
6	0.54	21	0.68	36	0.63
7	0.59	22	0.67	37	0.70
8	0.63	23	0.64	38	0.70
9	0.63	24	0.60	39	0.70
10	0.70	25	0.39	40	0.63
11	0.70	26	0.52	41	0.69
12	0.70	27	0.56	42	0.71
13	0.63	28	0.60	43	0.61
14	0.69	29	0.62	44	0.68
15	0.71	30	0.65	45	0.70

It is noted from Table (2) that the values of the corrected correlation coefficients for the relationship of items with the professional education values tool ranged from (0.71) to (0.39).

9.6 tool stability: For the purposes of calculating the internal consistency stability of the professional education values tool, Cronbach's α equation was used, depending on the data of the first application of the pilot sample, and for the purposes of calculating the consistency of repeatability; It was re-application on the exploratory sample by the test-retest method with an interval of two weeks between the first and second applications, where the Pearson correlation coefficient of the relationship of the first application with the second application of the exploratory sample was used, as shown in Table (3).

Table (3): The values of the internal consistency and recurrence coefficients for the vocational education values tool

Field	Stability transactions:		number Paragraphs
	Internal consistency	Replay	
School management	0.94	0.88	23
Curriculum field	0.86	0.84	11

Teacher's field	0.90	0.87	11
Values of vocational education	0.97	0.91	45

It is noted from Table (3) that the value of the internal consistency stability of the professional education values tool amounted to (0.97), while the value of the repetition stability of the tool reached (0.91).

While the value of the internal consistency stability for the domain of school administration was (0.94), the stability of repetition was (0.88), the value of the stability of the internal consistency for the domain of the teacher was (0.90), the stability of repetition (0.84), and finally the value of the stability of the internal consistency for the domain of the curriculum was (0.86), and the stability Redo (0.87).

9.7 Study tool correction standard: Likert scale was used for the five-year grading in order to measure the opinions of the study sample members, where it was given strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), strongly disagree (1), and the following classification was relied on. To judge arithmetic averages:

Length of the period = (highest value - lowest value) / 3 = (5-4) / 3 = 1.33

So it will be:

-Low approval score of (1-less than 2.33).

-Medium approval score of (2.34-less than (3.67).

-High approval score from (3.68-5).

10. Study variables

First: the independent variables

1. Gender, which has two categories; They are: (male, female).
2. Experience and it has three levels: (less than 5 years, from 5 to 10 years, and more than 10 years).
3. The job title has two levels: (teacher, supervisor).

Second: the dependent variable

The degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools in the northern region from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers.

11. The statistical methods used: To answer the study questions, the researchers used the appropriate statistical analyzes after entering the data on the computer, to analyze it using the (SPSS) program and to process it statistically. This is as follows:

-To answer the first question; Arithmetic means and standard deviations were used.

-To answer the second question; Means, standard deviations, and three-way analysis of variance (3-way-ANOVA) were used.

12. Study results and discussion:

First: the results related to the first question, which is: "What is the degree of possibility of applying the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in educational institutions from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers in secondary schools?"

To answer the question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the resolution domains as a whole, and for the paragraphs of each field separately, were extracted, and Table (4) the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the resolution fields as a whole illustrates this.

Table (4) Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the domains of the questionnaire as a whole

Field	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Rank	Grade
Curriculum field	3.83	0.73	1	High
Teacher's field	3.82	0.77	2	High
Managementfield	3.81	0.72	3	High
Arithmetic average values of total vocational education	3.81	0.71		High

Table (4) above shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the fields of study and the total arithmetic mean of the fields, where the most prominent of them were in favor of the "curriculum" field with an arithmetic mean of (3.83) and a high degree, while the field of "teacher" came in the second place with an arithmetic average of (3.82) and a high degree The field of "management" came in third place, with an arithmetic mean of (3.81) and a high degree, and the total arithmetic mean of the domains as a whole was (3.81) and a high degree.

The researcher attributes this result to the fact that the possibility of applying the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools is difficult due to several reasons, most notably: the lack of clarity of the basic concepts of the Islamic religion, the exclusion of specialists from Islamic law to formulate the vocational curriculum, the low social view towards vocational education, and the culture of The defect pervasive in society, the confusion of the educational system in Jordan, the absence of financial incentives for teachers and trainees, the weak partnership between the government and the private sector, the weakness of vocational guidance and counseling resulting from the multiplicity of authorities supervising vocational education, the weak scientific level of students transferring to vocational education, and the increase in the gap

between the theoretical side and practical. The results of the current study agreed with the results of the Al-Sharif study (2013), which showed the importance of manual labor as the best type of earning in Islam.

First: the field of school administration: The arithmetic means and standard deviations for the field of school administration were calculated, as shown in Table (5).

Table (5): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the field of school administration

Descending order	Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation	Grade
1	14	The school administration provides a program that helps students make the right choice of profession	3.97	1.00	High
1	22	The school appreciates the work of students within the school.	3.97	1.10	High
2	8	The school administration distributes the work to everyone fairly	3.95	1.07	High
3	21	The school administration is keen to develop the skill of critical and creative thinking among teachers	3.94	1.03	High
4	13	School management contributes to the professional growth of teachers periodically	3.93	1.05	High
5	1	The school administration engages all employees in formulating its vision	3.90	1.10	High
5	17	School management forms collaborative teams to achieve the school's goals	3.90	1.07	High
6	2	The school administration is developing its vision in line with professional educational developments	3.87	1.12	High
7	9	The school administration is keen to hold regular meetings with community members	3.85	1.08	High
8	16	School administration gives teachers participation in decision-making	3.84	1.04	High
9	19	The school administration is keen to constantly develop and update knowledge bases	3.79	1.06	High
10	15	School management stimulates education through work	3.78	1.08	High
11	6	The school's management supports the self-autonomy of teachers and empowers them	3.77	1.14	High
11	3	School management focuses on the quality of education according to the required standards	3.77	1.07	High
12	5	The school administration is interested in solving all the problems that happen in the school.	3.74	1.06	High
13	12	School management supports a culture of collaboration and teamwork between teachers	3.73	1.16	High
13	18	The school administration is drafting rules for work to which everyone is committed	3.73	1.13	High
13	23	The school administration is interested in creating positive human relationships between teachers	3.73	1.17	High
14	7	The school administration is concerned with cleanliness.	3.72	1.22	High
15	4	The school administration is interested	3.69	1.07	High

		in solving all the problems that happen in the school.			
15	10	School management encourages teachers and students to conduct studies that help develop professional work	3.69	1.09	High
16	11	School management responds to the requirements of the labor market and the community in high quality and content	3.66	1.10	High
17	20	The school administration provides an atmosphere of transparency and availability and exchange of information between teachers	3.60	1.16	Medium
Management			3.81	0.72	High

It is noticed from Table (5) that the arithmetic averages ranged between (3.97-3.60), as the paragraphs No. (14, 22), which state that “the school administration provides a program that helps students to choose the right profession, the school appreciates the students’ work within the school” in order The first, with an arithmetic mean (3.97), a standard deviation (1.00), and a high degree of practice, while paragraph No. (20) which states “the school administration provides an atmosphere of transparency and the availability of information and its exchange among teachers” came in the last order, with an arithmetic average (3.60). , standard deviation (1.16), with a mean practice score.

This result is attributed to the fact that vocational education schools have the ability to help students choose the appropriate vocational education for them, their appreciation of the students’ work, the prevailing atmosphere of justice over all workers within the schools and the development of critical thinking skills for all, and the prevailing atmosphere of transparency among some of the workers, but when looking at the reality within the vocational schools, they work to implement all of what was mentioned on the ground with paper only, and not to work with them, and that reason is the result of the difference in the social and ethical environment for the education personnel and the learners that work to enter the intermediaries and nepotism in school dealings, the student’s inability to choose the appropriate decision for him resulting from the lack of clarity in the future for him and the pressure of the parents on him to get rid of this type of education due to the society’s view of him and the nature of the educational environment within schools.

Second: Curriculum field: The arithmetic means and standard deviations for the curriculum domain were also calculated, as shown in Table (6).

Table (6): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the curriculum domain

Descending order	Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation	Grade
1	30	Professional program curricula include the theoretical and practical aspect	4.03	1.00	High
2	32	The curriculum encourages self-monitoring	4.02	1.04	High
3	29	New knowledge and science are added to the curriculum whenever needed	3.90	1.07	High
4	27	Curricula are available in accordance with international standards for professions	3.89	1.08	High
5	31	The curriculum instills in students a commitment to professional ethics	3.87	1.06	High
6	26	Curriculum developed as needed	3.83	1.06	High
6	28	The curriculum is permanently enriched to meet the needs of students	3.83	1.15	High
7	33	The curriculum encourages students to do manual work	3.77	1.14	High
8	34	The content of the curriculum is reviewed and determined to keep pace with the development of the labor market	3.72	1.22	High

9	24	The school has continuously developed curricula	3.66	1.25	Medium
10	25	The curriculum stimulates the spirit of competition among students	3.56	1.31	Medium
Curriculum field			3.83	0.73	High

It is noted from Table (6) that the arithmetic averages ranged between (4.03-3.56), as came Paragraph No. (30), which states that "the curricula of professional programs include the theoretical and practical side" in the first order, with an arithmetic mean (4.03), and a standard deviation (1.00), with a high degree of practice, while paragraph No. (25), which states that "the curriculum works to arouse the spirit of competition among students," came in the last order, with an arithmetic mean (3.56), a standard deviation (1.31), and a medium practice degree.

This result is due to the fact that the Jordanian educational system is making a great effort to keep pace with global developments by upgrading vocational education by placing it in the appropriate place within the educational system, due to its great role in changing the course of life and reducing poverty and unemployment, which has expanded in the Jordanian society significantly, and its impact on the economic income of the individual, and its role in the sustainable development of society, by developing vocational education, reducing the gap between the theoretical and practical aspects, encouraging students to practice manual labor, modifying the content of the curriculum to suit the labor market, and inciting the spirit of competition among students.

From the researchers' point of view, vocational education on the ground is completely different from these results, because the educational system is still concerned with the academic side at the expense of the practical side, and the gap between the practical and theoretical side is still increasing, the outputs of vocational education do not match the skills that the local market desires to possess for its pioneers; This reason is due to students evading from school, especially during the practical application days, and the poor treatment of school administrations towards the basis for vocational education in the basic stage in the subject of vocational education, by neglecting them and referring their quotas to other matters, including cleaning, compensation, and entertainment, among these issues is also the absence of parents' communication with school administrations, and the poor work environment that employs individuals who do not have the proper ethics of the profession; Which worked to avoid parents to send their children to go to those environments, and the competent authorities to develop plans without the participation of the school staff, which forces them to implement what was entrusted to them without exception.

Third: the teacher's field: The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the teacher's domain were also calculated, as shown in Table (7).

Table (7): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the teacher's domain

Descending order	Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation	Grade
1	41	Trust and mutual respect are available between teachers	3.97	1.00	High
2	35	Teachers are keen to apply the curriculum with modern educational strategies	3.95	1.07	High
3	40	Teachers take feedback into account	3.93	1.05	High
4	44	Qualified teachers are available to teach students	3.90	1.07	High
5	36	Teachers participate in the preparation of the curriculum	3.85	1.08	High
6	43	Equipment and equipment are tailored to the needs and capabilities of students	3.84	1.04	High
7	42	Teachers employ modern ICT to achieve vocational education goals	3.78	1.08	High
8	39	Teachers employ calendar results in school development	3.73	1.16	High
8	45	State-of-the-art equipment is available to help students teach professions	3.73	1.13	High
9	37	All teachers abide by the decisions made	3.69	1.09	High
10	38	All teachers are involved in implementing the decisions that are made	3.66	1.10	Medium
Teacher's field			3.82	0.77	High

It is noted from Table (7) that the arithmetic averages ranged between (3.97-3.66), as came Paragraph No. (41) which states "there is trust and mutual respect among teachers" in the first order, with an arithmetic mean (3.97),

and a standard deviation (1.00), with a high degree of practice, while paragraph No. (38) which states that “all teachers participate in the implementation of the decisions that are taken” came in the last order, with an arithmetic mean (3.66), a standard deviation (1.10), and a medium practice degree, and the total mean For the teacher's field (3.82), with a high degree of practice, while the total average of the values of vocational education was (3.81), with a high degree of practice.

The reason for this is due to the great role of teachers in implementing strategies, the impact of their participation in the formulation of the curriculum, the mutual respect between them and their use of modern technology in the implementation of the curriculum, and participation in decision-making. All these matters and others greatly help in achieving the desired goals and objectives of vocational education.

On the ground, researchers believe that there is no role for the teacher, whether in giving the educational material and applying the laws and regulations, and the reason for this is the weakness of the administrations and their lack of confidence in the teachers who were taught to put this view towards them, the confusion of educational policies and administrations, the weak financial situation of teachers, and the inferior view towards them. The teacher that was formed in the community due to the recent events that took place, the inability to distinguish between a good teacher from a bad one, the interest of teachers, parents and students in the theoretical side and neglect of the practical side, and the weakness of technical equipment and devices, and all these things worked to exclude the role of the teacher in forming and improving the outlook towards education professional.

Second: The results related to the second question, which is: “Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in educational institutions from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers in secondary schools that are due to the variables? (gender, job title, experience)?”

In order to answer the second question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in educational institutions were calculated from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools according to the variables of gender, job title, and experience, as shown in Table No. (8):

Table (8): Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in educational institutions from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools by gender, job title, and experience:

Variable	Level/category	Arithmetic medium	Standard deviation
Sex	Male	3.93	0.70
	Female	3.60	0.69
Experience	Less than 5 years	3.75	0.70
	5 to 10 years	3.85	0.77
	More than 10 years	3.83	0.65
Job title	Teacher	3.82	0.75
	Supervisor	3.81	0.69

It is noticed from Table (8) that there are apparent differences in the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in educational institutions from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools according to the variables of gender, job title, and experience. Three-way ANOVA, and Table (9) shows that:

Table (9): Results of the triple variance analysis of the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools according to the variables of gender, job title, and experience

source	Total squares	Degrees of freedom	Average squares	Value in	Significance
Sex	9.598	1	9.598	19.745	0.000
Experience	1.369	3	0.456	0.939	0.422
Job title	0.112	1	0.112	0.231	0.631
Error	183.261	377	0.486		
Total	193.632	382			

Table (9) shows that there are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of applicability of the values of vocational education in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools from the point of view of supervisors and teachers of vocational education in secondary schools due to the gender variable, and in favor of males over females. Where the arithmetic mean for males was (3.93), while it reached for females (3.60).

The reason for this is that the estimates of the study sample members believe that males apply the values of Islamic education in vocational education to females, and because males practice many professional works such as agriculture, industry and trade in a way that exceeds females, therefore, they are very keen to change the societal view of vocational education, and to highlight its true value stemming from the Qur'an and the Sunnah of the Noble Prophet, so that they direct young people to professional work away from shame, and strive to remove class barriers between members of society so that everyone becomes equal as the Lord of Glory and Glory be to Him and our Master Muhammad, may God bless him and his family and grant them peace.

The results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of applicability of vocational education values in the light of Islamic education in secondary schools from the point of view of vocational education supervisors and teachers in secondary schools due to the variables of experience and job title.

The reason for this is that the estimates of the study sample members, regardless of their job title (teacher, supervisor), or years of experience in education, seek to apply Islamic values in vocational education, because of its great impact of progress and prosperity in various scientific, industrial, and commercial fields, many countries of the world have sought to change the view of vocational education and put it on the right track. These countries have advanced and become leaders in their professional system.

Also, teachers and supervisors of vocational schools, regardless of their job title or experience, represent the top of the educational pyramid in their schools. They strive to be a good role model for their students in vocational schools by practicing some professional work with their own hands from an Islamic premise to urge students to adopt work values that will benefit them. The benefit is through providing them with a profession that earns them an income that helps them secure livelihoods, and its great impact in reducing the unemployment rates that have become afflicting the youth.

13. Recommendations

- 1- The Ministry of Education endeavors to develop positive trends towards vocational education, and to clarify its importance in the Holy Qur'an and the Noble Prophetic Sunnah.
- 2- The Ministry of Education's endeavor to instill moral values in students' hearts, such as the concept of honesty, perfection, and sincerity, in addition to establishing the concept that every Muslim is on a loophole in Islam, and that work becomes an obligation if the members of society do not perform it.
- 3- The Ministry of Education urged its professional teachers to set an example for their students in their appearance and behavior, and their eagerness to practice professional work themselves in order to set an example for students.
- 4- Extracting Quranic verses and noble Prophetic hadiths related to professions and insults, interpreting and classifying them in line with contemporary professions needed by the Muslim community, and presenting them to vocational schools to be a reference for them in all their practices.

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